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2 **Selecting the best technical fishway design for Iberian barbel, *Luciobarbus bocagei***

3 **(Steindachner, 1864): vertical slots versus submerged notches with bottom orifice.**

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16 **ABSTRACT**

17 When engineers and biologists face a fishway design, many issues need to be
18 considered, the type of fishway being the first and foremost. It is an especially complex
19 issue in areas with species whose migratory and swimming behavior are as yet poorly
20 known. The present study focuses on the capacity of the Iberian barbel (*Luciobarbus*
21 *bocagei*) to ascend two of the most common types of technical fishway on the Iberian
22 Peninsula: vertical slots, and submerged notches with bottom orifice. Both types were
23 studied and compared in terms of motivation (as the proportion of attempts and time
24 until the first attempt) and ascent ability (as the success rate and transit time).
25 Barbel did not show any difference in motivation between fishway types and easily
26 ascended both, although ascent was faster in the submerged notches with bottom orifice
27 fishway. Turning pools had a significant influence on transit time, resulting in a slight
28 delay, while smaller fish were slower in vertical slots.
29 These results may help fishway designers in their decision making, mainly in
30 Mediterranean areas with similar habitats and species.

31 **KEYWORDS**

32 Potamodromous fish, PIT tag, fish length, stepped fishways, turning pool, survival
33 analysis

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Transverse riverbed structures (dams, gauging stations, culverts, and others) have been
36 increasingly used in recent decades worldwide, leading to a high degree of current river
37 fragmentation (Baudoin et al., 2015). At the same time, there is progressively more
38 knowledge and environmental awareness about the need for free movement of
39 ichthyofauna along watercourses in order to complete their lifecycles.

40 In the case of the Iberian Peninsula, barriers to movement are among the principal
41 threats affecting endemic fish (Doadrio et al., 2011). One of the most common of these
42 species is the Iberian barbel (*Luciobarbus bocagei*). Like other potamodromous
43 cyprinids, barbels usually ascend to headwaters to spawn in spring. Their swimming
44 performance during migration period has recently been studied under field conditions,
45 showing a swimming ability similar to brown trout (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015, 2016).,
46 Many fish pass solutions have accordingly been designed in recent decades to improve
47 longitudinal connectivity. Technical stepped fishways have been the most popular
48 designs in Spain (Elvira et al., 1998), used first in salmonid areas and, since the present
49 century, in cyprinid reaches. Vertical slot fishways (VS) and submerged notch with
50 bottom orifice (SNBO) fishways are the most common types and there is no difference
51 in building cost between them. There are many references about their hydraulic
52 performance and design (Clay, 1995; Larinier, 2002; Fuentes-Pérez et al., 2014, 2016).
53 However, despite the particularities of Iberian rivers and ichthyofauna, field biological
54 assessments of these two types of fishway in terms of hydraulic features have been very
55 scarce (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2015, 2016; Rocaspana-Jove et al., 2012; Ordeix et al., 2011;
56 Aparicio et al., 2012). This means an added difficulty for engineers and biologists when
57 choosing the best fishway option.

58 The purpose of this paper is to evaluate and compare the capacity of the Iberian barbel
59 in terms of motivation, transit time and passage success in two of the most common
60 technical fishway types: VS and SNBO. The aim is to aid engineering design,
61 implementation and management decisions in many Iberian rivers and other
62 Mediterranean watercourses with similar species.

63 **2. Materials and methods**

64 2.1. Study site and fishways.

65 The experiments were carried out in two fishways at the Vadocondes (VS) and Guma
66 (SNBO) hydropower plants (River Duero, province of Burgos in north-central Spain;
67 41° 37' 59.1"N 3° 33' 44.3" W; Fig. 1). At these locations, the river drains a watershed
68 of 7398 km² with a mean annual discharge of about 17.5 m³/s (data from the
69 Vadocondes gauging station, code: 2522; www.saihduero.es). This river reach belongs
70 to the epipotamon area with an average altitude of around 810 meters above sea level.
71 The zone corresponds to category C6, i.e. a silt-clay bed stream of moderate sinuosity
72 with a slope of 0.001-0.02 m/m (Rosgen and Silvey. 1996), the most abundant native
73 fish species being the Iberian barbel.
74 Both fish ladders were built about 3 km apart. They were designed for cyprinids with
75 low volumetric energy dissipation <125 W·m⁻³ (Table 1; design details). Their bottoms
76 were covered by substrate from the riverbed to increase roughness, and discharge can
77 be regulated by a sluice gate located in the flow entrance.

78
79 **Fig. 1.** a) Study site location: Duero River, Castilla y León region (Northwest Spain). b)
80 Submerged notches with bottom orifice scheme (SNBO). c) Vertical slots scheme (VS). Black
81 slots: closing mesh; dotted circles: PIT antennas; striped pools: staging pools.

82 2.2. *Fish testing*

83 We used a Passive Integrated Transponder (PIT-tag) and antenna system to study how
84 fish face complex hydraulic flows during the ascent. Experimental fish were caught by
85 electrofishing one day prior to testing in a river branch 1 km downstream of the VS
86 fishway. For more details of handling procedures, see Sanz-Ronda et al., (2015).

87 **Table 1.** Geometrical characteristics of the fishway types. VS: Vertical slot; SNBO: submerged
88 notches with bottom orifice.

	VS	SNBO
Slope	6.52%	8.77%
Flow discharge*	$0.25 \pm 0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$	$0.27 \pm 0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
Volumetric Energy Dissipation**	$122 \pm 7 \text{ W}/\text{m}^3$	$121 \pm 10 \text{ W}/\text{m}^3$
Pool dimension (length x width x depth)	2.10 x 1.60 x 0.92 m	2.60 x 1.60 x 1.32 m
Height drop between pools	0.15 m	0.25 m
Width of the notches	0.20 m	0.30 m
Water velocity at the notches***	$1.48 \pm 0.08 \text{ m}/\text{s}$	$1.79 \pm 0.12 \text{ m}/\text{s}$
Bottom orifice size	None	0.20 x 0.20 m
Velocity at the orifices***	None	$1.94 \pm 0.09 \text{ m}/\text{s}$

89 *Obtained through dilution gauging, using Rhodamine WT, on previous trial dates

90 **Volumetric Energy Dissipation as the mean value of the pools under study

91 ***Direct measurements with a Model 2100 propeller meter (Swoffer Instruments Inc.)

92 2.3. *Trials*

93 Antennas were placed along each fishway, covering a height of 2.25 m (14 straight
94 pools in VS and 8 pools in SNBO, one of which was a turning pool with curved walls;
95 Fig. 1). Each antenna was connected to a dedicated reader (ORFID[®] Half Duplex
96 reader with a Multiplexer antenna), programmed to query the antennas at 14 Hz (3.5 Hz

97 or 0.29 s per antenna). Two Multiplexer antennas were used in all tests, both being
98 synchronized to avoid cross-talking phenomenon.

99 Just before each experiment, the fishway flow gate was opened to achieve the desired
100 water level and discharge flow (design conditions). Once established, the mesh at the
101 upstream end of the staging area was removed and fish were allowed to ascend the
102 fishway volitionally. Two homogenous groups of barbel per fishway did so, each trial
103 lasting 24 hours (Table 2).

104 Water level and temperature (Orpheus Mini, OTT Hydromet GmbH) were monitored in
105 both fish ladders throughout the day at 10-minute intervals.

106 *2.4. Data analysis*

107 Onset of movement:

108 In these trials, fish were able to make several ascents. Once fish reached the upper limit
109 of the fishway (closed with a mesh) or their maximum ascent distance (fatigue), they
110 usually descended to the resting pool, from where they could try to ascend again, thus
111 accounting for several attempts. Attempts were not considered valid unless the fish was
112 detected at antenna 2 so as to separate exploratory movements from ascent movements.
113 The last detection at antenna 1 was considered as the start time of the attempt. Attempts
114 where fish were detected at the antenna located at a height of 2.25 m were considered
115 “successful”; otherwise, they were considered “failures”.

116 Motivation:

117 Ascent motivation was analyzed in terms of two metrics: 1) whether or not barbels
118 made some attempt, analyzed via the chi-square test of independence; and 2) the time
119 since the beginning of the trial until the first attempt, which was quantified using
120 survival analysis, employing the Kaplan-Meier test and Log-Rank non-parametric test.

121 For this purpose, those fish that staged at least one attempt resulting in an uncensored
122 observation and those fish without any attempt were included as censored observations
123 with an attempt time equal to the duration of the trial.

124 Ascent analysis

125 Of those fish that staged attempts, ascent ability was analyzed using three additional
126 metrics. 1) Success: the proportion of ascending fish that reached the uppermost
127 antenna, analyzed via the chi-square test of independence. 2) Transit time: the time
128 needed to travel between the lowest and the uppermost antenna. Turning and straight
129 pools in SNBO were first compared using median comparison via the Kruskal-Wallis
130 test and then analyzed using Cox Proportional Hazard regression (PROC PHREG for
131 SAS) strata by attempt, assessing the influence of fishway type and fish length. 3)
132 Prediction of transit time as a function of fish length and the likelihood of its
133 occurrence, survival analysis based on regression models, fitted with PROC LIFEREG
134 and “Predict” Macro for SAS (Allison, 2010). Covariates were not considered to vary
135 over the time of the trials. In subsections 2) and 3), only successful attempts were
136 considered and transit time was converted into minutes per meter of ascent height, the
137 reference measure being the median and not the mean due to the non-normal
138 distribution of the data.

139 All statistical analyses were performed using SAS® (version 9.4) and Statgraphics
140 Centurion (version XVI.II) software.

141 **3. Results and discussion**

142 Testing was carried out during the spawning season (between 2nd and 7th June, 2012),
143 when barbel seemingly exhibit strong migratory activity in this area. Water temperature

144 varied between 18.3 and 20.5 °C, with no differences between experiments. The
 145 weather was stable, sunny and mild during trials.
 146 Flow discharge in both fishways was steady and close to design conditions. Very
 147 similar volumetric energy dissipation was generated in both fishways (Table 1).
 148 Results between two fish collections per fishway type were analyzed in a preliminary
 149 test, finding no significant differences between them in any of the fishways, neither in
 150 motivation nor in ascent parameters ($p > 0.265$ in all cases). Hence, both collections
 151 were merged for subsequent results.

152 **Table 2.** Sample size for the fish under study. Trial date: date and start time of trials, with a
 153 duration of 24 hours; Fishway: Vertical slot (VS) and submerged notches with bottom orifice
 154 (SNBO); Group: set of fish under study; Available: number of available fish; FL: mean Fork
 155 Length [minimum FL – maximum FL] (cm); K: mean \pm SD condition factor = $100 \cdot \text{mass} \cdot \text{FL}^{-3}$
 156 ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$). Attempting: total number of attempts (number of fish that staged attempts).

Trial date	Fishway	Collection	Available	FL [min-max]*	K*	Attempting
6/2/2012 18:30 h	VS	1	41	17.9 [11.0-24.0]	1.51 ± 0.18	129 (35)
6/4/2012 11:00 h	SNBO	2	41	17.3 [11.2-34.0]	1.49 ± 0.19	61 (23)
6/5/2012 14:30 h	SNBO	1	38	17.8 [11.0-24.0]	1.49 ± 0.20	56 (19)
6/6/2012 20:30 h	VS	2	33	16.8 [11.2-27.7]	1.52 ± 0.19	41 (6)

157 *There were no significance differences between fishways and/or collections

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159

160 *3.1. Motivation analysis*

161 1) Analyzing the number of fish that staged some attempt versus the total number of
162 available fish, there were no differences between fishway types (VS = 55.4 % and
163 SNBO = 53.2 %; $p = 0.781$).

164 2) Regarding time from the beginning of the trial until the first attempt, no differences
165 were found between the two types of fishway (median time: VS = 0.49 min and SNBO
166 = 64 min; $p = 0.557$).

167 According to these results, motivation may be considered similar for both fishway
168 designs.

169 *3.2. Ascent analysis*

170 1) Success was similar between fishways for the first attempt (VS = 92.7% and SNBO
171 = 90.5%; $p = 0.718$) and when taking into account all the attempts (VS = 95.6% and
172 SNBO = 93.7%; $p = 0.532$).

173 2) As the turning pool may affect and delay transit time (Thiem et al., 2011; Silva et
174 al., 2015; Marriner, 2014, 2016; Nijssen et al., 2015), a comparison between this pool
175 and the straight sections was first carried out for successful attempts in SNBO. There
176 were significant differences between the two (median time for a height of 1 meter:
177 turning pool = 8.2 min and straight sections = 4.2 min; $p < 0.001$). Subsequently, to
178 compare both fishway types in terms of transit time, only straight sections in SNBO
179 were considered, the ascent being faster in this latter design (median time for a height
180 of 1 meter: VS = 6.1 min and SNBO = 4.2 min; $p = 0.040$).

181 In any case, these ascent values for barbel in VS and SNBO were lower than for the
182 same species and type of fishways with higher volumetric energy dissipation. For
183 instance, barbel needed 18.9 min/m in a straight VS fishway with 185 W/m^3 (slope 8%;

184 drop between pools 0.2 m) (Sanz-Ronda et al., 2016) and 22.3 min/m in a SNBO
185 fishway with 181 W/m^3 and one turning pool (slope 8.8 %, drop between pools 0.25 m)
186 (Bravo-Córdoba et al., 2016 in rev.). This inverse relationship between volumetric
187 energy dissipation and passage efficiency has been reported in the scientific literature
188 (Santos et al., 2012; Fouche et al., 2013), volumetric energy dissipation probably being
189 the easiest and one of the most common parameters used by fishway engineers to
190 indicate how good the structure is for fish ascent (Kynard et al., 2011). The possibility
191 of fatigue or learning during the ascent was taken into account, but no pattern was
192 observed between antennas to support either hypothesis.

193 Fish length, on the other hand, was found to be an influential covariate, showing a
194 negative correlation with transit time for VS ($p = 0.0037$), but not for SNBO ($p =$
195 0.387), smaller individuals seemingly needing more time to ascend VS. A number of
196 studies have reported a similar relationship between barbel length and swimming speed
197 (Silva, 2011; Sanz-Ronda, 2015), though others such as Thiem et al. (2011) did not find
198 this relationship in the case of lake sturgeon in VS.

199 3) For VS, a predictive model of the proportion of fish ascending as a function of fish
200 length was calculated (transit time per meter of height). The best-fitted model
201 (Akaike's Information Criterion) was log-logistic regression (Fig. 2). Based on this
202 model, the effect could be expressed approximately as transit time reduced by $(\exp(-$
203 $0.0646)-1) = 6.2\%$ per cm increased in fork length. Despite size differences between
204 the 10th and 90th percentiles not being very large (approximately 8 cm), the maximum
205 difference in the sample was about 23 cm. Thus, the influence of fish length was
206 considered important in ascent time. Studying the same species and similar sizes, Sanz-

207 Ronda et al. (2015) likewise found a superior swimming endurance in larger
208 individuals.

209 4. Conclusions

210 The contribution of this study is to provide criteria for the selection and design of
211 fishways and, in particular, for the Mediterranean barbel: *Luciobarbus bocagei*, as
212 numerous structures of these types are soon to be built in their native area. Based on the
213 results presented here, both VS and SNBO have a similar good performance for a wide
214 range of fish lengths under the trial design assumptions. However, ascent times were
215 slightly faster for SNBO, though assuming no important migration delays in both types.
216 Turning pools must be considered to have an effect in this species and further research
217 is needed regarding their influence. Ascent ability can be modeled, constituting an
218 interesting tool for future comparisons between other fishway types or target species
219 and sizes.

220

221 **Fig. 2.** Vertical slot predictive model (log-logistic) for the proportion of fish ascending (1 m of
222 height exceeded) at a given transit time as a function of fish length.

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